

ML objectives	User Experience Perspective				Infrastructure Perspective	
Problem & context The disproportionate burning of gases causing high money costs.	Accountability The operator is completely responsible for decisions taken in order to reduce the burning gases.	Cost The operator shall be aware of the sanctions in case of not preventing bad burning gases.	Forcefulness Other system shall use the predictions to take automatic actions in the refinery.		Data streaming The videos shall be streamed by accessing the IP address of the camera that points at the flare.	
Organizational goals Increase the refinery's profitability through an efficient safe flare gas burning.	Frequency The operator shall receive a classification of the flare every minute.	Interactiveness The system shall grow data by receiving feedback from user interactions.	Value The operator shall have transparency on the reduction of bad burning gases.	Visualization The predictions of the model shall be presented in a dashboard in an interactive way according to the approved prototype.		Execution engine The model shall be deployed to internal customer servers and consumed locally.
User goals The gas burning classifications shall be accurate allowing the operator to activate the automatic work mode	Data Perspective					Incremental Learning The images shall be continuously used to retrain the model.
	Baseline The images shall meet the constraints (e.g., pixel coordinates, dimensions), defined in the baseline dataset.	Data operations ^E The images shall be extracted from videos, cropped and labeled as needed.	Distribution ^E The images shall be split in some rationale degree into training and test data.	Quantity ^E The training and test dataset shall have images as needed to build a valuable model.	Source The images shall be obtained from videos that are sent by the customer due to permission issues.	
Model goals Accuracy, precision, recall >= 70%	Timeliness The videos from a month ago shall be available for use		Inherent data quality The images shall meet bias, completeness, consistency, credibility and real usage.			Integration The model shall be integrated with an inference engine so that it can define operation operation rules.
ML functionality Classify through computer vision techniques the gas burning state of the flare.	Model Perspective					Storage The ML artifacts shall be stored in a cloud service on Microsoft Azure and recovered in an efficient way.
	Algorithm ^E Neural Networks	Explainability Does not apply	Inference time The model shall infer a set of images (40) in less than a minute.	Input \ Output ^E Input: images reflecting all the flare burning states Output: Image classified	Learning time Training the model shall take one day at most.	
Leading indicators Percentage of use of the automatic work mode and reduce the money costs of burning gases	Maintainability The model creation shall follow best coding practices (e.g., coding conventions PEP-8, SOLID design principals) and be documented according to docstring PEP-257.	ML problem type Classify images (computer vision technique)	Model performance The model shall be correct at least 70% of the time.	Model size The model size shall not break the inference time.	Reproducibility The creation/training of the model shall be automated by using a pipeline.	Telemetry The system shall collect summary data from user interactions so that it can be monitored.
Customer expectations The system shall accurately classify the flare when burning gases.						